

MUTUAL LEARNING AS A CONDITION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE MOBILITY IN FUTURE EDUCATORS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8247410>

Abstract. *The article discusses the role of cognitive mobility in the education of future educators. A theoretical analysis was also carried out and cognitive mobility was defined as an integrative quality of a person, including motivational, creative and reflexive components that characterize the readiness and ability of a person to constructively solve problems in the changing conditions of modern pedagogical reality.*

Keywords: *cognitiveness, mobility, creativity, motivational component, reflexive component, pedagogy, psychology, effectiveness, training, method.*

The dynamically changing modern world and the nature of the ongoing changes in all spheres of life urgently require a person to have qualities that allow him to effectively navigate the diversity of the surrounding reality, creatively and productively approach any changes. This stimulated the emergence of new goals and values in the system of vocational education, focused on the intellectual and creative education of future specialists, among which the development of cognitive mobility of the individual is of no small importance.

According to scientific definitions, mobility (French *mobile*, Latin *mobilis* - mobile) is interpreted as the ability to move quickly, transform and interact under the influence of changing conditions of activity. Mobile is considered a person of a new, modern formation, capable of improving, flexibly responding to new requirements and conditions of existence and adapting to them; it is characterized by an active life position in activity, which determines the orientation in life, readiness for practical action. A number of scientists consider the processes of social and professional-pedagogical development of a person in unity with the development of mobility as a socially and professionally significant ability.

Mobility is of particular importance in the professional activity of a teacher. Complicated in content, taking place in dynamic conditions, with an abundance of simultaneously acting factors, pedagogical activity requires the teacher to be able to find optimal solutions in a timely manner in changing situations of reality. Therefore, cognitive mobility becomes a necessary element of the teacher's personality, which determines the nature of his activity, the ability to recognize and evaluate the difficulties and contradictions of various aspects of professional activity, to independently and constructively resolve them in accordance with their value orientations, to consider any difficulty as an incentive for further development, which in general determines the effectiveness of pedagogical work.

The conducted theoretical analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature allowed us to define cognitive mobility as an integrative quality of a person, including motivational, creative and reflexive components that characterize the readiness and ability of a person to constructively solve problems in the changing conditions of modern pedagogical reality.

The motivational component of cognitive mobility integrates such qualities as personality activity, cognitive needs, positive motivation, which determine the motivation for cognitive activity, the success and productivity of its implementation in various situations.

The basis of the creative component of cognitive mobility is initiative, manifested in a creative focus on understanding reality, self-detection and formulation of problems, search for their solutions, and creativity, characterized by openness to new experience, the ability to abandon stereotypical ways of acting, behavior and produce diverse ideas based on changing conditions.

The reflexive component of cognitive mobility is expressed in criticality, aimed at evaluating the ideas put forward in terms of their compliance with the requirements of the situation under study, and reflexivity as a property of a person that provides the ability to correlate one's actions with a problem situation and coordinate them in accordance with changing conditions.

The selected components are closely interconnected and together characterize the level of not only cognitive, but also holistic personal development, which makes it possible to define cognitive mobility as the optimal condition necessary for the professional and personal growth of a future teacher. Cognitive mobility provides a high level of pedagogical skill and competence, creates opportunities for educating a student's mobile personality, capable of self-development, independent moral choice, and competition.

It is obvious that the development of cognitive mobility in future teachers will be most effective if special conditions are created for this. In our opinion, one of these conditions is mutual learning based on the communication and interaction of students in the process of learning.

The effectiveness of this method of cognition has been proven by centuries of pedagogical practice. The idea of interaction between students is set forth in Plutarch's description, in the Confucian principles of the great teaching, in the Talmud, where all aspects of Jewish life are regulated. The medieval English education system, the pedagogical system of the Catholic order of the Jesuits, was built on the principles of mutual learning. In the history of education, the idea of cooperation was established in the works of many famous teachers.

Appeal to various forms of student co-organization was characteristic of many experimental schools of the late 19th - early 20th centuries: self-government, educational cooperative, mutual aid circles, consultant method, group, collectively distributed, jointly divided methods of organizing cooperation in teaching by teachers. The conducted research allowed teachers to draw important conclusions that for full-fledged learning and development, a student needs communication and joint activities (including educational ones) not only with adults, but also with peers.

In psychology, group interactions have been studied in various aspects. The socio-psychological aspect reveals the possibilities of psychological support and assistance in the group. It is called social facilitation: the very fact of the presence of other people activates the personality, positively influencing the effectiveness of its activities. The cognitive aspect is based on the ideas of J. Piaget and L.S. Vygotsky, emphasizing the special role in the process of intellectual development of the personality of the factor of social interaction and interpersonal communication. According to J. Piaget, in the process of joint activity, participants are involved in discussions that give rise to cognitive conflicts and the desire to resolve them, which stimulates thinking and the development of cognitive abilities. In the cultural-historical theory of L.S. Vygotsky, it was shown that social interactions, which initially act as tools for the social implementation of the processes of thinking and communication, later begin to play the role of the cognitive function of self-

regulation and the mental representation of this or that information. These interactions activate as yet undeveloped cognitive functions, allowing the learner to function at a higher cognitive level.

The results of psychological and pedagogical research formed the basis of many modern progressive pedagogical technologies, largely based on the intensive involvement of the group's socio-psychological potential (problem-based, developmental learning, technology of collective learning (CSE), project method, technology of collective thought of activity, etc.).

In line with the search for a new content of educational interactions in pedagogical science, interactive learning appears, built on interaction (interaction), cooperation, cooperation of equal participants in the educational process. Mutual learning as a special type of learning interactions is a process of cognition, where knowledge is obtained in joint activities through a dialogue, a polylogue of students among themselves. In the course of joint activities, participants observe each other's actions, exchange ideas, methods of action, thus transferring and adopting the accumulated experience, which allows the individual not only to actualize his internal potentials, but also to enrich the intellectual, emotional, and activity spheres. It is very important that interactive learning changes the nature of interactions with the teacher: his activity gives way to the students' activity, his main task is to create conditions for their initiative. In such training, students do not act as passive "learners", but as full participants, their experience is no less important than the experience of a teacher, who does not provide ready-made knowledge, but encourages independent search.

Thus, the organization of mutual learning, based on the positive interdependence of participants, cooperation, mutual support and mutual enrichment, can have a positive impact on the development of their cognitive mobility in educational and cognitive activities.

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